

OBSERVATION OF BANDING FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF CFRTP LAMINATES WITH FIBER DISCONTINUITY USING DIC

K. Onozuka¹, K. Iizuka² and S. Yoneyama¹

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Aoyama Gakuin University
5-10-1, Chuo-ku Huchinobe, Kanagawa, Japan

Email: c5625184@aoyama.jp, web page: <https://www.me.aoyama.ac.jp/~yoneyama/>

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Aoyama Gakuin University
5-10-1, Chuo-ku Huchinobe, Kanagawa, Japan

Email: iizuka@me.aoyama.ac.jp, web page: <https://www.me.aoyama.ac.jp/~yoneyama/>

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Aoyama Gakuin University
5-10-1, Chuo-ku Huchinobe, Kanagawa, Japan

Email: yoneyama@me.aoyama.ac.jp, web page: <https://www.me.aoyama.ac.jp/~yoneyama/>

Keywords: CFRTP, Fiber Discontinuity, DIC, FEM Analysis, Three-points Bending Test

ABSTRACT

This study presents the observation of damage behavior under bending of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) with fiber discontinuity. CFRTP with high strength is utilized for a variety of situations such as airplane and foot orthoses. However, CFRTP is well-known as weak for compression, especially the buckling in the situation of remolding foot orthoses. The resin rich region existing in fiber discontinuity is considered to reduce the buckling. The three-points bending test result indicates the discontinuous CFRTP has 82.0% bending strength and 84.0% shear strength compared to the continuous CFRTP. The continuous CFRTP is damaged on the compression side surface. A tiny crack may cause injury in the situation of utilization for foot orthoses. Micro scale tensile test using laser microscope for the consideration of fracture mechanism shows the strain concentration at both edges of resin rich region. This strain concentration is considered to cause damage. This means the discontinuous CFRTP is useful for foot orthoses.

1 INTRODUCTION

Foot orthoses require light weight, high strength, design ability. CFRTP with a high specific strength and modulus is utilized such as vehicle and aircraft. In recent years, CFRTP has become relatively more affordable, and its application in medical devices such as orthoses is considered. When CFRTP is utilized for foot orthoses, it is subjected to bending stress in order to adjust to physical growth. However, fiber's buckling is occurred on the compression side under bending. Delamination also tends to appear on CFRTP laminates. A tiny crack may cause injury in the case of foot orthosis. The resin-rich region existing in the fiber discontinuity is considered to reduce the fiber deformation under bending. This study presents an observation of the damage behavior under bending of CFRTP (CF/PMMA) laminates with fiber discontinuity. Digital image correlation (DIC) is utilized to observe displacement and strain distributions.

Fig. 1.1. Schematic diagram of shear fractural behavior

2 THREE-POINTS BENDING TEST

Prepregs with a length of 40mm are stacked with a shift of 10mm to make fiber discontinuity as shown in Fig. 2.1. After molding, the laminated plate is cut into test specimens for three-points bending test. In three-point bending test, a total of six types of test specimens, with thicknesses of 3.0 mm, 3.5 mm, and 4.0 mm, are prepared from CF RTP laminates with fiber discontinuities and continuous fiber CF RTP laminates. Three samples of each type are tested. The test specimen names are assigned as shown in Table 2.1 for identification. Due to dimensional variations when cutting the specimens, the measured dimensions after cutting each specimen are shown in Table 2.2.

Fig. 2.1. Schematic diagram of discontinuous CF RTP specimens

Table 2.1. Numbering of specimens

	Thickness		
	3.0mm	3.5mm	4.0mm
Continuous	c3-1, c3-2, c3-3	c3.5-1, c3.5-2, c3.5-3	c4-1, c4-2, c4-3
Discontinuous	d3-1, d3-2, d3-3	d3.5-1, d3.5-2, d3.5-3	d4-1, d4-2, d4-3

Table 2.2. Thickness and width of specimens

Number	h[mm]	b[mm]	Number	h[mm]	b[mm]
c3-1	2.97	15.40	d3-1	3.05	15.30
c3-2	2.95	15.41	d3-2	3.03	15.22
c3-3	2.93	15.39	d3-3	3.00	14.95
c3.5-1	3.40	15.58	d3.5-1	3.59	14.93
c3.5-2	3.37	15.46	d3.5-2	3.67	15.00
c3.5-3	3.48	15.01	d3.5-3	3.51	15.08
c4-1	3.94	15.25	d4-1	4.03	15.07
c4-2	3.98	15.35	d4-2	4.03	14.93
c4-3	4.09	15.49	d4-3	3.98	14.89

In this experiment, the span between the supports is set to 25 mm, and the testing speed is 1.0 mm/min. A schematic diagram illustrating the testing setup is shown in Fig. 2.2.

Fig. 2.2. Three-points bending test

Figure 2.3 shows displacement and strain distribution obtained from d3-1. Focusing on the strain in the y-direction, interlaminar delamination (stripe-shaped strain concentration) is observed on the center

in the thickness direction of the specimen. Figure 2.4 shows displacement and strain distribution obtained from c3-1. Compression damage (strain concentration on the diagonal direction) is observed on the surface of the specimen. The bending and shear strengths are evaluated based on the loads at which these damages are observed.

Fig. 2.3. Displacement and strain distribution of d3-1 at 140s

Fig. 2.4. Displacement and strain distribution of c3-1 at 140s

Table 2.3 shows the flexural strength or shear strength obtained from each specimen. When comparing the shear strength of the 3.5 mm-thick specimens and the flexural strength of the 4.0 mm-thick specimens, it was found that the CFRTP laminates with fiber discontinuities retains 82.0% of the flexural strength and 84.0% of the shear strength compared to the continuous fiber CFRTP laminate.

Table 2.3. Bending strength and Shear strength

Continuous			Discontinuous			Ratio[%]
Sample number	Bending strength [Mpa]	Shear strength [Mpa]	Sample number	Bending strength [Mpa]	Shear strength [Mpa]	
c3-1	424.2	-	d3-1	-	18	
c3-2	410.5	-	d3-2	-	16.4	
c3-3	382.7	-	d3-3	-	15.6	
avg.	405.9	-	avg.	-	16.7	-
c3.5-1	-	23.6	d3.5-1	-	21.4	
c3.5-2	-	22.7	d3.5-2	-	21.2	
c3.5-3	-	22.8	d3.5-3	-	15.4	
avg.	-	23.0	avg.	-	19.3	84.0
c4-1	312.7	-	d4-1	225.7	-	
c4-2	285.2	-	d4-2	256.0	-	
c4-3	243.3	-	d4-3	208.5	-	
avg.	280.4	-	avg.	230.1	-	82.0

By observing the detected damage with a laser microscope, the influence of such damage on practical applications, such as orthoses, is considered. Figure 2.5 shows the compressive fracture and interlaminar delamination caused by bending observed by the laser microscope. The white, stripe-like features visible in

the image correspond to fiber area oriented in the x -direction. Since the specimen used in this experiment is a plain-woven fabric, fiber area aligned in the z -direction appear as dark, elliptical shapes. Compressive fracture due to bending is accompanied by fiber buckling. The fracture surface of fibers exposes on the specimen's surface.

Fig. 2.5. Damage behavior observed by laser microscope

Finite element analysis (FEM) is used to simulate the three-point bending test, calculating the stress distribution as well as the displacement and strain distributions. The FEM software used for the analysis is Marc Mentat, and an elastic-plastic analysis is performed. A resin-rich region made of acrylic is introduced within the CFRTP to reproduce the fiber discontinuity. The material properties used in the analysis are shown in Table 2.4. Additionally, the model and boundary conditions used in the analysis are shown in Fig. 2.6.

Table 2.4. Material constant for FEM

PMMA	CFRTP		
$E=1.0\text{GPa}$	$E_{xx}=53.1\text{GPa}$	$\nu_{xy}=0.20$	
$\nu=0.35$	$E_{yy}=1.0\text{GPa}$	$\nu_{yz}=0.20$	$G_{xy}=2.5\text{GPa}$
	$E_{zz}=53.1\text{GPa}$	$\nu_{zx}=0.05$	

Fig. 2.6. Fiber discontinuities for FEM model

Figure 2.7 shows the stress distributions obtained by FEM. Since the maximum compressive and shear stresses occur below the indenter, damage may be expected in this area. However, due to the indenter constraining out-of-plane deformation, the damage does not appear. It is considered that the deformation is small. When the fiber discontinuity is close to the surface, stress concentrations for both compressive and shear stresses occur. The location where the fiber discontinuity is situated in the second layer from the surface is where the compressive and shear stresses are most likely to concentrate.

(a) Stress distribution in x -direction

(b) Shear stress distribution

Fig. 2.7. Stress distribution obtained by FEM

3 TENSILE TEST

To focus on a single fiber discontinuity within the specimen, the specimen is cut that the fiber discontinuity is located at the center of the specimen. The dimensions of the specimen and the position of the fiber discontinuity are shown in Fig. 3.1. In order to observe the specimen with a laser microscope, the specimen is polished with sandpaper in the following order: 600, 800, 1000, 1500, and 2000 grit, and finally polished with a polishing compound to confirm the position of the fiber discontinuity. The fiber aligned in the x -direction appears as white streaks under observation. Since the test specimen used in this experiment is woven fabric, fibers in the z -direction appear black and elliptical. The resin portion appears bright white. The image of the fiber discontinuity captured with the laser microscope is shown in Fig. 3.2, where a 1.39 mm resin-rich area is observed.

Fig. 3.1. Schematic diagram of discontinuous CFRTP specimen

(a) Resin rich region (b) Random pattern for DIC

Fig. 3.2. Resin rich region and random pattern for DIC observed by laser microscope

Fig. 3.3. Tensile test machine

Figure 3.4 shows a load-time diagram obtained from tensile test. The displacement and strain distributions at 190 seconds are shown in Fig. 3.5. The black dashed line in the distribution indicates the location of the resin-rich region at the fiber discontinuity. Focusing on the strain in the x -direction, strain concentrations are observed at both ends of the resin-rich region.

Fig. 3.4. Load-time diagram

Fig. 3.5. Displacement and strain distribution

FEM is used to simulate the tensile test, calculating the stress distribution as well as the displacement and strain distributions. The FEM software and the material properties used in the analysis are the same as the previous section. The model and boundary conditions used in the analysis are shown in Fig. 3.6. The boundary conditions are set to fixed displacements at both ends, as in the experiments. The applied load is set to 500 N, based on the load-time curve obtained from the experiment.

Fig. 3.6. Fiber discontinuity of FEM model

Fig. 3.7 shows the displacement and strain distribution obtained from the FEM analysis. Focusing on the strain in the x -direction, strain concentrations are observed at both ends of the resin-rich area, consistent with the experimental results. However, in the strain distribution obtained from the experiment, strain concentration appeared in a scattered manner.

Fig. 3.7. Displacement and strain distribution calculated by FEM

4 CONCLUSION

To explore the application of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) laminates in orthoses, three-point bending tests were conducted using short-beam specimens. Two distinct failure modes were observed: Mode II interlaminar shear failure, and compressive failure on the compressive surface caused by fiber buckling. The CFRTP laminates with discontinuous fibers retained 84.0% of the shear strength

and 82.0% of the flexural strength compared to their continuous-fiber counterparts. Thin CFRTP laminates were found to be more susceptible to interlaminar delamination. Additionally, continuous-fiber CFRTP laminates tended to exhibit compressive failure under bending, which was accompanied by the occurrence of micro-damage on the surface. Considering the potential for such micro-damage to cause injury in the context of orthoses, the use of discontinuous fibers is considered beneficial.

To investigate the potential for discontinuous fiber regions to serve as damage initiation sites on the tensile surface during bending, tensile tests using a laser microscope were performed. Strain concentration was observed at both ends of the resin-rich region associated with the discontinuous fiber area. A similar tendency was confirmed through finite element method (FEM) analysis, suggesting that these strain concentrations may act as origins of damage.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to the Suzuki Foundation for their generous support, which enabled participation in ICCM24.

REFERENCES

- [1] Nakatani, H., Nakaya, K., Matsuba, A., Kouno, Y. and Ogihara, S., Effect of Prepreg Cut on the Mechanical Properties in CFRP Laminates, *Journal of Solid Mechanics and Materials Engineering*, Vol, 5, (2011), pp. 742-752.
- [2] Fikry, M., Atikah, N. and Ogihara, S., Microscopic Damage Behavior of Angle-ply CFRP Laminates with Fiber Discontinuous Plies, *Materials system*, Vol, 37, (2020), pp. 65-72.
- [3] L. Sorensen, T. Gmür and J. Botsis, Delamination propagation measurement using long gauge-length FBG sensors, *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Composites Testing and Model Identification CompTest 2006 (Eds. P. Camanho, F. Pierron, M. Wisnom), Porto, Portugal, April 10-12, 2006*, University Press, Porto, Paper 41, 2006, pp. 174-175.
- [4] Alott, N. and Czabaj, M., Characterization of the interlaminar shear strength of IM7/8552 using small-scale short beam shear tests, *Elsevier*, Vol. 142, (2021)
- [5] Fikry, M., Wang, Q., Irita, M., Ri, S., Toyama, N., Vinogradov, V. and Ogihara, S., Measurement of microscopic strain distribution of CFRP laminates with fiber discontinuities by sampling moiré method, *Advanced Composite Materials*, Vol. 31, (2022), No. 3, pp. 273-288.